

Enhancing Mechanical Performance of Recycled CF/PEKK Composites: The Role of Strand Optimization and Plasma-activated Adhesive Bonding in Sandwich Structures

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Abstract

- **Improved skin/core bonding** → Atmospheric Plasma Activation (APA)
- **Tailored skin material and manufacturing technique together with sustainability consideration** → The use of R-ROS composite panel
- **Realization of the improved sandwich structures** → APA treatment with R-ROS skin composites.

Methodology

1 Manufacturing of recycled CF/PEKK ROS composite skins

2 Quality assurance of skins

- Pick the strand size
- Void Analysis
 - Warpage Measurement
 - Micro-CT
 - Tensile Test + DIC
 - Shear Test + DIC
 - Compression Test
 - Izod Impact Test
 - DMA
- Scan me for the optimal strand size

3 Manufacturing of sandwich composite structures

4 Quality assurance of sandwich composite structures

- Microscopy
- Flatwise Tensile Test
- Edgewise Compression Test
- 4-point Bending Test
- Charpy Impact Test

Results and Discussion

More randomized strand orientation and improved inter-strand interactions → Short Strand Sandwich Composite with R-ROS skin

Conclusion and Outlook

- The vacuum-assisted hot press manufacturing technique proved effective in producing R-ROS composites with aerospace-grade quality at a low cost.
- The skin/core bonding interface is improved through atmospheric plasma activation (APA) treatment, preventing any separation.
- The recycled short ROS composites can be a good candidate to replace thermoset composite in sandwich structures as the core material serves as a structural stabilizer.

